

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF KHARIF GREEN CHILLI GROWERS IN AURANGABAD DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract:

The present study was carried out during the year 2020-21 in Aurangabad district of Maharashtra state to know the socio-economic status of chilli growers. Aurangabad district comprise of 9 tehsils in which two tehsils namely Sillod and Soygaon were purposively selected. Three villages were selected from each tahsil which is Amthana, Pendgaon and Dharla from Sillod and from Soygaon villages selected were Soygaon, Galwada and Furdapur in which highest area under Chilli cultivation. From each village 15 chilli farmers were selected randomly thus total sample size were 90 farmers. Data were collected by means of personal interview with the help of pre structured schedule.

Most of the farmers were younger and capable for working. The 99 per cent farmers were literate, so they can easily understand about policies and recommendations related to agriculture. The result indicated that in the family size there was 35.78 per cent males, 32.60 per cent females and 33.77 per cent were children. Majority of the farmers were engaged in Agriculture. Majority of the farmers are small farmers. The average size of land holding was 3.49 ha. Chilli and cotton were the main crops in selected study area.

Keywords: Socio-economic status, Chilli farmers, Cropping pattern.

Introduction:

Chilli (*Capsicum annum*), is a valuable crops of India. It is grown almost throughout the country. Chilli is also known as 'hot pepper' and capsicum (Shimla Mirchi) as 'bell pepper.' The Portuguese came with capsicum from Brazil to the India during the year 1584. Chilli is a fruit of the plants 'capsicum frutescens' and 'capsicum annum.' Chilli comes from the genus 'capsicum,' and it is belonging to the family of 'Solanaceae'. Chilli fruits are small in size and known for their sharp acidic flavour and colour.

The red colour of chilli because of the pigment 'capsanthin,' biting pungency due to the pigment 'capsaicin.' Chilli is considered as one of the best spices used in the Kitchen. The paste of chillies acts like as appetizer. Due to presence of Capsaicin compounds, chilli pepper is used in the preparation of ointment; also used in formulation to be used in arthritic pain and sore muscles. Chilli are used as medicine in diarrhoea, pain and sprain, numbness, heart attack, diabetes.

Methodology

The sampling technique followed was purposively Multistage sampling procedure was adopted for selection of district, tehsils, villages and the chilli growers. The sampling procedure adopted for the study is given below. At first stage Aurangabad district was purposively selected. In second stage two tehsils viz. Sillod and Soygaon was selected. In third stage three villages was selected from each tehsil. List of chilli farmers was collected from revenue record of each village and from each village 15 chilli cultivator's was selected constituting a total sample size 90. The study was based on both

primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected through personal interview method from farmers, with the help of well-structured and pretested questionnaire exclusively designed for the study. The data collected from chilli growers by personal interview method with the help of pretested interview schedule and pertaining for the year 2020-2021.

Result and Discussion:**Socio Economic Characteristics Of Chilli Growers:****Age groups:**

The result indicated that in the age group, 21-30 years there was 33.33 per cent farmers, in 31-40 years age group there was 26.66 per cent farmers, in 41-50 years age group there was

28.88 per cent farmers and above 50 years age group there was 11.11 per cent farmers were present. That means most of the farmers were younger and capable for working. (Table 1).

Educational status:

The result indicated that 38.88 per cent farmers were educated up to college level,

24.44 per cent farmers were educated up to higher secondary, 22.22 per cent farmers were educated up to secondary level, 13.33 per cent farmers were educated up to primary level and

1.11 per cent farmers were illiterate. That means 99 per cent farmers were literate, so they can easily understand about policies and recommendations related to agriculture. (Table 1).

Family size:

The result indicated that in the family size there was 35.78 per cent males, 32.60 percent females and 33.77 per cent were children. (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of chilli growers

Sr. no.	Particular	Numbers (N=90)	Percentage
1.	Age in year		
	21-30 years	30	33.33
	31-40 years	24	26.66
	41-50 years	26	28.88
	Above 50 years	10	11.11
2.	Education		
	Illiterate	1	1.11
	Primary	12	13.33
	Secondary	20	22.22
	Higher secondary	22	24.44
	College level	35	38.88
3.	Family size		
	Male	2.14	35.78
	Female	1.95	32.60
	Children	2.02	33.77
4.	Occupational level		
	Agriculture	65	72.22
	Service	7	7.77

	Business	18	20
5.	Land holding		
	Up to 2 ha	38	42.22
	2 to 4 ha	25	27.77
	Above 4 ha	27	30
6.	Livestock position		
	Bullock pair	1.00	31.15
	Buffalo	1.09	33.95
	Cow	1.12	34.89

Occupational level:

The result indicates that 72.22 per cent farmers were engaged in agriculture sector, 18 per cent were engaged in business sector and 7.77 per cent were engaged in service sector. That means majority of the farmers were engaged in Agriculture. (Table 1).

Land holding:

42.22 per cent farmers have up to 2 ha land holding, 27.77 per cent farmers have 2 to 4 ha land holding and 30 per cent farmers have above 4 ha land holding. That means majority of the farmers are small farmers. (Table 1).

Livestock position

The result indicated that 34.89 per cent farmers were possess cows, 33.95 per cent farmers were possess buffalos and 31.15 per cent farmers were possess bullock pairs. That means farmers were possess both milch and draft animals. (Table 1).

Land use pattern of chilli growers

The result indicated that the irrigated area was 95.41 per cent, while rainfed area was 4.58 per cent. That means most of the land was under irrigation. There was 100 per cent net sown area. 4.49 ha area was gross cropped area. The cropping intensity was 128.65. The average size of land holding was 3.49 ha. (Table 2).

Table 2: Per farm land use pattern of chilli grower

Sr. no.	Particular	Area (ha)	Per cent
1.	Irrigated area	3.33	95.41
2.	Rain fed area	0.16	4.58
3.	Net sown area	3.49	100
4.	Total area	3.49	100
5.	Gross cropped area	4.49	---
6.	Cropping intensity	128.65	---

Cropping pattern of chilli growers:

The result indicated that the farmers grow their crops in three seasons i.e. *kharif*, *rabi* and *summer*. The result indicated that the 4.49 ha was the gross cropped area. Out of gross cropped area, under chilli crop it was 0.47 ha i.e. 10.46 per cent. 0.59 ha area was under maize crop i.e. 13.14 per cent. Cotton is the main crop in the selected area having 1.63 ha. area i.e. 36.30 per cent. 0.35 ha area was under soybean i.e. 7.79 per cent. 0.45

ha area was under ginger

i.e. 10.02 per cent. Then 0.43 ha area was under wheat i.e. 9.57 per cent. 0.57 ha area was under chickpea i.e. 12.69 per cent. 0.31 area was under bajra i.e. 6.90 per cent. 0.25 ha area was under groundnut i.e. 5.56 per cent. That means the total area under *kharif*, *rabi* and *summer* was 77.71, 22.26 and 12.46 respectively. This result revealed that 128.65 per cent was the cropping intensity and 22.27 per cent was the double cropped area. (Table 3).

Table 3. Cropping pattern of chilli growers:

Sr. no	Particular	Area (ha)	Per cent
A.	<i>Kharif</i>		
1	Chilli	0.47	10.46
2	Maize	0.59	13.14
3	Cotton	1.63	36.30
4	Soybean	0.35	7.79
5	Ginger	0.45	10.02
6	Subtotal	3.49	77.71
B.	<i>Rabi</i>		
7	Wheat	0.43	9.57
8	Chickpea	0.57	12.69
9	Subtotal	1.00	22.26
C	<i>Summer</i>		
10	Bajara	0.31	6.90
11	Groundnut	0.25	5.56
12	Subtotal	0.56	12.46
13	Gross cropped area	4.49	100
14	Double cropped area	1	22.27
15	Net cropped area	3.49	77.71
16	Cropping intensity	---	128.65

Conclusion:

Most of the farmers were younger and capable for working. 99 per cent farmers were literate, so they can easily understand about

policies and recommendations related to agriculture.

Majority of the are small farmers were engaged in Agriculture. The cropping intensity was 128.65. The average size of land holding was

3.49 ha.

Fig. 4.1 Area status of selected chilli growers

Fig. 4.2 Cropping pattern of chilli growers to gross cropped area

Fig.4.3 Double and net cropped area of chilli growers

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